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P(ISSN) : 3007-0031

E(ISSN) : 3007-004X

<https://rc-archive.com/index.php/Journal/about>

Graphic Design Education and Graphic Design Industry in Pakistan

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Publisher : EDUCATION GENIUS SOLUTIONS

Review Type: Double Blind Peer Review

ABSTRACT

This research explores the evolution and current status of graphic design education and industry in Pakistan. As a vital component of the fine arts, graphic design reflects diverse aspects of visual culture and serves as a communicative tool to inform and engage society. Since independence in 1947, Pakistan's design industry has evolved alongside global trends in media, technology, and advertising. The establishment of *Orient Advertising* in 1953 and *Packages Limited* in 1956 marked key milestones in professional design and packaging innovation. Later, international agencies such as *J. Walter Thompson* and *Ogilvy & Mather* introduced modern corporate design practices to the local market. In recent decades, academic institutions including the National College of Arts and the University of the Punjab have advanced specialized programs in graphic and communication design, fostering both theoretical understanding and practical skills. Simultaneously, the rise of digital platforms has expanded freelance opportunities, with thousands of Pakistani designers contributing to the global creative economy.

This study highlights how graphic design in Pakistan has grown from traditional print media into a dynamic, technology-driven discipline that integrates art, communication, and cultural identity, playing a vital role in shaping contemporary visual culture and creative industries.

Key Words: Graphic Design Education, Visual Communication, Creative Economy, Cultural Identity, Pakistan.

This research will discuss the status of graphic design education as well the related industry in Pakistan. Graphic Design is a component of Fine Arts represents different forms of the visual culture encountered the people unconsciously or consciously on daily basis. Though design can also be used for information, or it can delude the viewer, but its major purpose is to create awareness and inform people. Graphic designing is one of the leading industries worldwide. As technology is getting advanced, more opportunities are coming for graphic designers. Within the freelancing world, there is a massive number of people earning a livelihood from graphic design.

Graphic Design Industry in Pakistan

Graphic/Communication Design in Pakistan has generally followed the trends and innovations adopted globally. It has responded to the changing business environment, media technologies and cultural and ethical pick-up lines. In 1947 soon after the independence there had been very few mediums of advertising and all of these were only covering the local population at the time.

The communication industry in Pakistan grew over time. In the beginning the local businesses were utilizing the available medium that was mostly newspapers, magazines and reading digests etc.

In Pakistan most graphic designers are working as a freelancer on

Upwork, Fiverr, and other big freelancing platforms.¹ Regarding the educational backgrounds, so many are a bachelor's in arts or have taken short or long courses from big to small size institutions. Under these circumstances, Pakistani freelancers are more into graphic designing as compared to other fields. There are 171 companies in Pakistan, which provide graphic design services. The design industry in Pakistan is booming and so is the scope of graphic designing. Graphic designers are in high demand in Pakistan. Many reputable brands and industries are always on the lookout for creative individuals, the salaries are quite good too.

Graphic Design plays a significant role in the overall development of various design forms practiced in Pakistan, and presently there are many institutions that are offering successful degree and diploma programs in this discipline. It is seen that due to the academic development in this discipline; graphic designing has contributed a lot for promoting the industry. In Pakistan graphic design related industry mainly comprises the advertising industry which has different mediums for advertising purpose. Starting from poster art to billboard designs then photography and afterwards there comes the trend of digital development (interactive design) etc.

In 1953, well established advertising agency by the name of Orient was founded by S.H. Hashmi (1935-2006). Afterwards in Karachi more rapidly small advertising agencies started up their proper setups. Moreover, top international agencies like J. Walter Thompson (JWT) and then Ogilvy & Mather established their country head offices in the same city. It is important to mention here the establishment of Packages limited, in 1956 at Lahore, as a joint venture by Ali Group of Pakistan and Swedish firm, becoming one of the largest Packaging design industries of Pakistan engaging the graphic design graduates. During the decade of 2005-2015 multimedia design came into view. Today it encompasses app and game design as major mediums for communication.

Graphic Design Education in Pakistan

The fruits of Industrial Revolution did not remain limited to the West. The British colonization paved the way for institutionalization of art and craft education in the Subcontinent.

Early Art & Design Institutes in Sub Continent were:

- Bombay School of Art in 1857.
- College of Arts Kolkatta in 1884 (teaching pottery, tile making, metal crafts.) Later in 1950,s these institutions started the program of Graphic Design named as (Commercial/Applied Arts)

In the last quarter of 19th century crafts schools were established in the Subcontinent. In the region that later became Pakistan, Mayo School of Art emerged as a pioneering institution of craft education geared towards supporting industrial production. It

¹ Khan and Ali. "Chronicling Graphic Design Trends of Pakistan Postage Stamps" (1948-2018). *PUTAJ Humanities and Social Science* 27, no. 2 (2020): 95-119.

was also called Mayo Memorial School of Industrial Design and Industrial School of Art and Design.

The essential focus of art education in the British period, which included training in various skills that can be seen as precursors to Graphic Design, was not to create highest merits of aesthetics but to produce professionals for the growing industrial needs. Architecture, textile design and printing, and a diverse range of traditional crafts and manufacturing were the focal elements in the artistic landscape of Pakistan.² After Partition, the situation altered, and we observe a major transition. Under Ayub Khan's military regime, a new agenda of modernization was introduced, and various measures were taken to make educational institutions to be at par with Western counterparts. The Mayo School of Arts became the National College of Arts in 1958 under the directives of the government. The National College of Arts now had various departments, mainly Department of Fine Arts, Department of Architecture and Department of Design. In 1963, the College was taken from the Department of Industry and came under the Department of Education. Meanwhile, The Department of Fine Arts at Punjab University (elevated to Punjab University College of Art & Design in 2007) also introduced degree program in Graphic Design in 1964. Anna Molka Ahmed (1917-1994) was a prolific Pakistani artist and pioneer of fine arts. Anna Molka started off with a class of 23 girls. From the very first day, Anna Molka's commitment and personal interest in her students was obvious to all. Anna devised a program of art teaching, starting the classes with theory, practice and history.

Anna delivered a series of radio lectures and wrote numerous newspaper articles focusing on creativity and the intention of the artist; modern methods of art teaching; and other art education-related matters. In 1962, Department of Fine Arts in Peshawar University introduced Diploma in Publicity Design and two years later a degree program. The Karachi School of Art established in the 1960s also provided formal education in Design. Design courses also found their place in National College of Textile Engineering in Faisalabad. In the 1970s, University of Sindh and Balochistan University started and offered undergraduate degrees in Design. The National College of Arts, previously awarding Diplomas was given the status of Degree Awarding institution in 1985. MFA in Design also got instituted at Peshawar University.

In 1988, another vision was taking shape that was an Art and Architecture School for Karachi. Professors Zahoor Ul Akhlaque advised the alumni to divert their energies towards creating a new institution of Art. Initially it began with National College of Arts as a role model. In 1989, Indus Valley School of Art and Architecture

² Tarar, Nadeem Omar. "Aesthetic Modernism in the Post-Colony: The Making of a National College of Art in Pakistan" (1950-1960s), *International Journal of Art & Design Education* 27, no. 3 (2008): 332-45, <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1476-8070.2008.00587.x>.

was started which offered degree in Graphic Design. Later, a visit from Ashoke Chatterjee, professor and pioneer of National Institute of Design, (NID), in Ahmedabad, India - one of the leading Design schools of the world - inspired IVS to form linkages with it. Along with David Alesworth, Shahid Rajput (Head of Communication Design) and Khalid Omari (coordinator of Architecture) visited NID to closely look at their curriculum, its implementation and the teaching methodology. IVS adopted system of Foundation Year and attempted to do away with the system of grades and instead have qualitative reports from the relevant faculty.

Graphic Design in Pakistan has generally followed the trends and innovations adopted globally. It has responded to the changing business environment, media technologies and cultural and ethical pick-up lines. In 1947 soon after the independence, there had been very few mediums of advertising and all of these were only covering the local population at the time. The communication industry in Pakistan grew over time. In the beginning, the local businesses were utilizing the available medium that was mostly newspapers, magazines and digests.

By mid-1990s, a whole institution focused on Design education was established in Lahore, i.e., the Pakistan School of Fashion Design (PIFD). In the first decade of 21st century, more Graphic Design endeavors started in institutions like Beaconhouse National University and Lahore College for Women University.³ The last two decades, under the directives of Higher Education Commission of Pakistan (HEC), saw a transition from the academic vision of art education to that of a contributor to industry. There are different graphic design institutes in Pakistan, some of them are mentioned below.

- Fine Arts Department, University of the Punjab (now Punjab University College of Art & Design, PUCAD), Lahore
- National College of Art (NCA), Lahore
- Indus Valley School, Karachi
- Department of Visual Studies, Karachi University, Karachi
- Institute of Design & Visual Arts, Lahore College for Women University, Lahore
- Beacon House National University (BNU), Lahore
- Fine Arts Department, University of Baluchistan, Quetta
- Department of Art and Design, University of Peshawar, Peshawar

However, a focus on the philosophical, aesthetic and social aspects

³ There were many other institutions formed that had courses in Graphic Design. To name some of the newly formed departments and colleges are Department of Fashion and Design, Sarhad University (2001); School of Textile Engineering, Faisalabad University (2002); Department of Art & Design, AJ & K University, and Multan College of Arts, Bahauddin Zakariya University (both in 2003); Textile Institute of Pakistan, Karachi (2004); Department of Fine Arts, Sardar Bahadur Khan Women's University, Quetta (2005); Departments of Art & Design and Architecture, Hazara University, Mansehra (2008); School of Creative Arts, The University of Lahore and so many others in the line.

of art education was maintained by the HEC.

Pakistan has a diverse and rich culture including the creative, artistic and inventive heritage. Today various art and design creative practices are displayed at international level with very strong impact.⁴ Just like many developing countries its urban centers and middle-class population is considered with newer opportunities and international connections for Pakistani people. In Pakistan graphic design has now attained a prominent position amongst various cultural and recreational areas and covers about 44.2% employment in the design sector.⁵ Though at earlier time when this field was introduced; it was seen that only there were few institutions offering diploma in this field, but later different institutions have flourished due to the contribution and services of different academicians and professionals. Currently there are many professional graphic designers who have attained their education from Pakistani institutions and currently they are serving at different international reputable organizations and media houses. One such example is of graduates of computer graphics from national institutes successfully working in Hollywood Animated Productions.

Shahnawaz Zaidi⁶ states that graphic design education in Pakistan started as a craft to contribute industrial requirements, then gained an academic identity, afterwards became a market-oriented research and practice to ensure that industry has a well-equipped workforce. However, Zaidi mentions that it is intriguing that the changing relationship of graphic design education and its corresponding industry has not been documented.⁷

The absorption of graphic designers in the communication industry of Pakistan and the hundreds of students graduating in the discipline create this illusion that the process is much tangible and result oriented. Even a cursory observation reveals that this surge is due to the economic forces and not due to creative and aesthetically inspiring potential of the discipline. According to M. H. Jafri there is a need to examine graphic design education and its impact on industry in our indigenous setting, so that the necessary changes could be made within the domain of graphic design education which will bring positive changes within the graphic

4 Vandal, Sajida H. "Art Education In Pakistan: A Case Study of Bringing Art To School Children At The Informal Level," UNESCO Regional Expert Symposium on Arts Education in Asia, (Hong Kong 2004).

5 Evans, Keith, Sam Stockley, Calvin Taylor, Julie Brown, Maryam Rab and Sumbul Khan, "Cultural and Creative Industries in Pakistan." British Council (Lahore 2014) 25.

6 Shahnawaz Zaidi Art & Design Educationist, Former Principal College of Art & Design, University of the Punjab, Lahore, Pakistan. (In Zaidi's tenure as Head of Fine Arts Department, graphic design curriculum was re-established as per German BAHAUS methodology, which was initiated by Anna Molka Ahmed, one of the pioneers of Fine Arts education in Pakistan Advisor Design, COMSATS Lahore Campus and Pakistan.

7 Shahnawaz Zaidi, Graphic Design II, September 29, 2020.

design industry in Pakistan.⁸

In South Asia, specifically Pakistan, design is often manipulated in a manner that it beholds the nationalist and patriotic agendas of those in power.⁹ The influence that design has on masses and how it can build a specific narrative is inevitable. Since, design is the main fundamental cultural interpretation. The effect it can have on intersectionality is multi-fold. In South Asia, people are often discriminated based on their social class, ethnicity, religious ideas, education level and gender. These discriminations are often rationalized, intentionally or unintentionally, by the ruling class to keep their influence relevant for the masses. The role that design can play to counter such negative effects of intersectionality is significant for the discovery.¹⁰ According to Iram Zia Raja the study of graphic design is a very important area in terms of design as well as economics, since Pakistan is a textile producing and manufacturing country and textile is one of its major exports.¹¹

When National College of Arts (NCA) was established in 1958, textile design had a very predominant place in its curriculum. As NCA was founded on industrial needs, it still maintains its legacy as a school for industry requirements. Textile and industry have a significant relation with each other in Pakistan. Currently courses offered at different Pakistani schools of design also have an industrial approach as a part of their vision. Pakistani people think of prints and patterns often as textile design; however, design is much more than this.¹²

In international design schools, different modules are being taught with specialized classes for sculpture making, weaving, dyeing etc. however, in Pakistan, students hardly specialize in this major. The industrial aspect of design is often neglected by the Pakistani youth because they do not have the orientation and thus cannot anticipate a bright future for them. In the field of weaving, although there is a growing trend in the Subcontinent, there are number of emerging brands that deal in excellent weaving options but print-designs in textile industry still await improvement. The growing trend of lawn fabric in Pakistan has increased requirement of designers in the textile industry.¹³ South Asian

⁸ M. H. Jafri is a Design Practitioner in Packages Lahore, Pakistan Design Educationist, a Professor and the Former Head of Communication Design Department, National College of Arts, Lahore, Pakistan.

⁹ Idrees, Afrah. "*The Brown Stripe in Pride: Exploring South Asian Queer Liberation through Graphic Design.*" Ryerson University, 2020.

¹⁰ Iram Zia Raja, Graphic Design XI, March 12, 2021. Head of Textile Design, National College of Arts,

¹¹ Iram Zia Raja is a design educationist, Head of Textile Design Department at National College of Arts, Lahore

¹² Nasir, Saadia, Prakash Vel, and Hafsa Mateen. "Social Media and Buying Behaviour of Women in Pakistan Towards the Purchase of Textile Garments." (2012): 61.

¹³ Kashif, Shumaila, and Shujaat Mubarik. "An Evolutionary Historical Perspective of Pakistan Retail Fashion Industry." *JISR Management and Social Sciences & Economics* 18, no. 1 (2020): 53-75.

region has been making textiles for millennia now, and it is an ancient art with a rich history pertaining to the textile design. However, the design students are not being taught about the importance of the history of the local arts and crafts of the sub-continent as it is entirely missing from the curriculum. "The reason that there is no proper bridge between industry and academia in Pakistan is that the history and techniques related to the craft of textile in Pakistan is not well preserved."¹⁴ Amjad Parvez a senior professor of graphic design commented that there is a disintegration between indigenous techniques and modern Western methodologies.¹⁵

Rahat Naveed,¹⁶ a senior professor of art & design emphasized that in the context of the rich design history of the Subcontinent, people in Pakistan lack the awareness of their own heritage even to the extent that the material that other people might see as craft, for them might just be everyday wear.¹⁷ For example, if one is wearing something that is a vegetable dye block print for them it is as equivalent to another mass-produced fabric. Rahat further explained that one does not necessarily see it as some sort of artisanal craft being an heirloom product because people in the Subcontinent have such crafts in abundance.

Ahmed Mir,¹⁸ an emerging name in textile design industry, states that although government in Pakistan is making effort for the textile sector, still special support for craft textiles is direly needed. It might die out if they keep on lacking the support and hence eventually will be lost forever. Modern textiles from South Asia have a rich heritage. They are immersed in folklore and bound within history of international trade.¹⁹

The journey of Pakistani art is manifold. It absorbs the extensive history of colonialism, nationalism, and globalization. It is connected to graphic design from postmodernist perspective and pursues to ratify its site in the modern world of visual arts.²⁰

¹⁴ Shafiq, Muhammad, Flevy Lasrado, and Khalid Hafeez. "The effect of TQM on Organisational Performance: Empirical Evidence from the Textile Sector of a Developing Country using SEM." *Total Quality Management & Business Excellence* 30, no. 1-2 (2019): 31-52.

¹⁵ Amjad Parvez is a Graphic Design Educationist and Founding Director Press and Publication, University of the Punjab, Lahore.

¹⁶ Art Educationist, Former Principal College of Art and Design, University of the Punjab, Lahore. (In her tenure as a Principal curriculum was revised and updated in 2012)

¹⁷ Saddiqa, Aisha, and Nida Ijaz. "An Analytical Study of Design Configurations in Pakistani Paintings." In Proceedings of the 2nd International Conference on Design Industries & Creative Culture, DESIGN DECODED 2021, 24-25 August 2021, Kedah, Malaysia. 2022.

¹⁸ Animation Practitioner, Pioneer of FRAG Games in Pakistan.

¹⁹ Maxwell, Robyn. *Textiles of Southeast Asia: Trade, Tradition and Transformation*. Tuttle Publishing, 2012.

²⁰ Memon, Ghulam Rasool. "Education in Pakistan: The Key Issues, Problems and the New Challenges." *Journal of Management and Social Sciences* 3, no. 1 (2007): 47-55.

Graphic design has become a practical discipline of education and a central feature of modern communication industry. Before the arrival of computer aided design, communication of an idea to the masses through graphic designs involved a combined operation of six kinds of specialists.²¹ A designer was assigned to create a page layout, a typesetter was given the task to create the text in the required font while the pasting and positioning of the text required a production artist. A photographer produced negatives, which would be assembled together. The process went on to include plate makers to prepare printing plate and at last through a press operator the product got finalized.²² In the 1990s, all these operations were reduced to a single man's job, who with the help of a computer and printer, would perform all tasks in a ridiculously efficient way.²³ The computer age revolutionized graphic design education and related industry, and the revolution was perpetual. When asked about the technological advancement and its use in the graphic design related industry in Pakistan, Nadeem Bashir explained that even today there is still more to learn about software application, more effective computer hardware and other related interventions like 3d printers and motion capturing technology.²⁴ Innovations are encouraging us to view the subject from a wider perspective with each passing day.²⁵

A visit from Ashoke Chatterjee, Professor a pioneer of National Institute of Design, (NID), in Ahmedabad, India_ - one of the leading Design schools of the world - inspired Indus Valley School to form linkages with it. Along with David Alesworth, Shahid Rajput (Head of Communication Design at that time) and Khalid Omari (Coordinator of Architecture), visited NID to closely look at their curriculum, its implementation and the teaching methodology. The emerging technology and the integration of various specialized roles has made the graphic designer a much more enabled and influential tool for the modern communication industry. Jessica Helfand stated that modern culture refers to the multidisciplinary process of using typography, images, and increasingly some combination of media to teach, instructs or persuade a specific audience to do something as graphic design. Such persuasive techniques are both conceptualized and to varied degree carried out by the graphic designers. In their capacity as messenger of communication they create solutions for the presentation of

²¹ Ahmad, Riaz, and Hong Mi. "Arts and Social Sciences Journal." *Arts and Social Sciences Journal* 8, no. 2 (2017).

²² Timothy, Samara. "Making and Breaking the Grid: A Graphic Design Layout Workshop." *Gloucester, MA: Rockport* (2017).

²³ Meggs, Philip B., and Alston W. Purvis. *Meggs' History of Graphic Design*. John Wiley & Sons, 2016.

²⁴ Design Educationist, Head of Visual Communication Design, National College of Arts, Lahore.

²⁵ Bashir, Zia, Nadeem Iqbal, and Muhammad Hanif. "A Novel Gray Scale Image Encryption Scheme Based on Pixels' Swapping Operations." *Multimedia Tools and Applications* 80 (2021): 1029-1054.

abstract facts by materializing concepts. They design logos and film titles as well as books, periodicals, exhibitions, posters, and packaging.²⁶

According to Helfand's view, graphic designer is a promising tool for the modern communication industry. However, it is to ponder that whether qualified designers available in the field. Pakistan even though a developing country outpaced by developed countries in terms of creating graphic design technologies, has universal increase in technology as compared to that of the West.²⁷ The institutional patronage of graphic design education and the growing communication industry of Pakistan, particularly in the last couple of decades, have produced many individuals who are working in the communication industry and some of them are setting significant benchmarks with a few registering themselves in the international arena of excellence. However, the general output of the institutions and that of industry need to be much more channelized and upgraded. This is an important task since the reach and potential of graphic design industry is mind boggling when it comes to shaping the intellectual and emotional orientation of a society. The West recognized it in the 1960s as it becomes clear with the Charles Wright Mill's ideology, who believed that men's existence does not determine their awareness of their consciousness. There are the ways of communication, design, pattern, and ideas which have a significant influence on the human psyche and on the physical world.²⁸ The principal vehicle of this consciousness is the public arts, design arts and mass parts.

According to Murtaza Jafri, the role of graphic designer in shaping the consciousness of the masses has become manifold and significant with two important developments in communication industry.²⁹ The first took place in Pakistan with the arrival of satellite channels in addition to state-owned Pakistan Television Network. This development increased the consumption of graphic designers in the communication industry at a considerable rate.³⁰ The competitive environment created by the arrival of new channels demanded a higher quality in designs and advertisement strategies. Increase in the number of channels meant more commercials, more graphics, and a higher quality for aesthetic uplifting of this visual impact. The second development, which by implication, is more efficient when it comes to shaping a culture in the social media. It transformed the way people communicate and access information and in the present culture, social media has

²⁶ Jessica Helfand, "Hey, Mr. Design Man" News, *Los Angeles Times*, accessed May 29, 2018, <http://articles.latimes.com/2001/jan/28/books/bk-17901>.

²⁷ Cifelli, Samara. "Emilio Pucci: Revolutionizing Textile Design."

²⁸ Mills, C. Wright, and Irving Louis Horowitz. "Power, Politics and People: The Collected Essays of C. Wright Mills." *Science and Society* 28, no. 4 (1964).

²⁹ Murtaza Jafri an Art and Design Educationist, Principal/Rector, National College of Arts, Lahore; Graphic Design VIII, December 22, 2020.

become the most powerful tool to communicate ideas to the masses. A fresh overview of such changes and growing role of graphic design education and industry linkage is therefore paramount for future course of action.

There are two principal areas of concern when it comes to an evaluation of pedagogical approaches in universities and its potential implications on industry. First, the nature of curriculum that is being taught in leading institutions and the second is the product of the university, which is the graphic designer.

Graphic Design as a Tool of Communication

With the advent of the internet and social media, the world today is the arena of communication, be it visually or otherwise hence, the role of graphic design is inevitable. The professional industry of graphic design requires designers to be able to understand the aesthetics of graphic design while keeping the industry in mind. A graphic designer must have the consciousness of cultural, social-political, and religious aspects of customers before designing anything. It is essential to understand the psychology of the customer and any of his related historic background. To visually communicate any message to the audience, it is essential to understand what the observer is deriving out of it given their cultural and psychological context. According to Quentin Newark, graphic design is the collection of all the arts.³¹ Graphic designing is how one gives meaning to the visuals around him. Today, we cannot escape graphic designs especially in our urban culture. Amy E, Arntson defined graphic designing as “the design of things people sees and read.”³² According to Arntson, when a graphic designer tries to create a visual imagery, he communicates with the aesthetics of the observer through his design.

In the processes of communication, everyone needs a certain medium, be it words or gestures or even a surface or an object. What makes an artist distinct from the rest is the power to change mundane objects or surfaces into aesthetic pieces which translate into emotions or feelings. Arntson considered graphic design as problem solving, and she clarified that “problems in graphic design almost always relate to visual communication, and there are specific methods of creating a design that communicates visually and conceptually.”³³ From Arntson’s point of view, it could be presumed that graphic design solves problems visually. As problem solving is to make complicated issues simpler, Hembree stated, “graphic design serves as a method for improving society through effective communication that makes complicated things easier to understand and use” hence graphic designing is problem solving through communication.³⁴ This communication can be visual as

³¹ Newark, Quentin. "What is Graphic Design?" (2002).

³² Arntson, Amy E. *Graphic Design Basics*. Cengage Learning, 2011.

³³ Arntson, 3.

³⁴ Hembree, Ryan. *The Complete Graphic Designer: A Guide to Understanding Graphics and Visual Communication*. Rockport publishers, 2006.

well as cognitive. Many people distinguish graphic design from arts simply because art is creative, whereas graphic designing is more problem solving and problem solving is a branch of creativity hence, graphic designers can be called artists as well.³⁵

Graphic design is finding a creative source to communicate, which itself is an art. However, Hembree argues how graphic designing cannot be categorized as art since the purpose of both is different. Although both processes are creative, graphic designers must use their tools to effectively communicate and, hence systematically follow required steps. Since graphic designers are seen as graphic intellectuals and critical thinkers, they deliver a concert using different mediums such as papers, concrete surfaces, ink, and colors in order to convey their idea to their customers, they are mostly called message makers as well.

Marty Neumeier asserted that the process of visual communication is like a monologue. The components to a graphic message and a monologue are the same i.e. a sender, a message and a receiver.³⁶ The graphic designer involves the customer into this creative process as the receiver and interpreter of the message. The delivered message must remain with the receiver for long as it touches their aesthetics and beyond. According to Salima Hashmi, the designer must connect with the customer on the level of perception, emotion, cognition, sensation, sound, and identification.³⁷

Technology and Education

In modern times, technology is indispensable to education. Contemporary learning is systems involving technological adherence to maximum level. Education sector has transformed completely. From traditional pedagogical approaches to recent digital shifts causing major changes in policy making. According to Antonio Bowen, technology has effectively improved teaching and learning by optimizing classrooms and digitizing courses. Technology ensures meaningful interactions of students with their teachers and increases their learning capacity by ensuring digital resources are available, seamlessly. The power that technology has endowed to the educators is undoubtedly preeminent. Technology not only helps in the teaching and learning process but also plays an eminent role in curriculum development. Although there is no doubt in the importance that technology holds in the field of education, it has become increasingly challenging to ensure a successful transition from traditional school systems to digital systems. The curriculum development being a constructive step in advancement in education is merely the first step towards

³⁵ Barnard, Malcolm. *Graphic Design as Communication*. Routledge, 2013.

³⁶ Neumeier, Marty. "The Brand Gap-How to Bridge the Distance Between Business Strategy and Design. New Riders." (2006).

³⁷ Salima Hashmi is Art Critic, Art and Design Educationist, Former Principal National College of Arts, Lahore (She worked extensively on the art and design teaching pedagogy in Pakistan); Graphic designer IV, November 5, 2018.

educational development in graphic design. Real challenge lies in ensuring effective implementation of the developed curriculum. As students of millennial generation, we are accustomed to technology and digital adaptation is not a challenge for them. Bowen highlighted importance of human capacity in the education system which not only attributes to the change in teaching and learning methodology but also efficient ways of implementing those changes. He has advocated the use of virtual learning beneficial for both students as well as teachers.³⁸

Bowen suggests to the teachers and faculty members to ensure maximum inclusion of students in the teaching and learning process by enabling them in technological endeavors. One such suggestion is the use of e-portfolios. He has highlighted importance of e-portfolios in ensuring uninterrupted and resourceful learning with technological development. Scholars also highlight the importance of technology in the learning process by stating that technology has helped teachers perform their duties in a more effective and efficient manner. The teaching capability of instructors has accelerated multiple times with the use of technology. He added that technology is not mainly about computers, cell phones or iPods but it is sophisticated and seamless way of letting students and teachers interact in a more meaningful way without any interruptions.³⁹

Technology is being increasingly used by teachers across the world, there are several benefits attached to it. One of the main reasons is that it gives the teacher access to a wide array of digital tools. Students can enjoy audio-visual resources which gives an edge to the process of teaching and learning. Technology is also very useful in meeting requirements of different students who might find it difficult to learn in a traditional learning environment. The third advantage according to Sharon Smaldino is that technology optimizes a well-designed curriculum meant to meet needs of diversity of students. A modern-day curriculum cannot be implemented without audio-visual aids; hence technology remains the center of curriculum development. Smaldino asserted that to cater different learning styles of students, learning methodologies need to be planned aptly while ensuring that instruction is meaningful as well as resourceful for the students. This education planning, if deliberated properly merging diverse learning methods, could produce the vital outcome of effective teaching and learning. Technology is a significant tool to encourage students towards independent learning. As per Ruth Geer and Trudy-Ann Sweeney, the fundamental reason for incorporating technology into learning is to ensure independent learning in students where they are

³⁸ Bowen, José Antonio. *Teaching Naked: How Moving Technology out of Your College Classroom will Improve Student Learning*. John Wiley & Sons, 2012.

³⁹ Simonson, Michael, Susan M. Zvacek, and Sharon Smaldino. "Teaching and Learning at a Distance: Foundations of Distance Education: 7th edition." (2019).

provided with the resources and tools to learn at their own pace. They further added that “information and communication technologies (ICT) are essential tools in today’s world; the use of ICT provides opportunity for students to learn in multiple ways and in multiple spaces.”⁴⁰ In their study, Geer and Sweeney conclusively admitted that technology has not only enabled students but teachers too. Geer and Sweeney further deduced that student, when given the opportunity to interact with technology, feel more empowered and well-equipped which eventually also helps the instructor achieve the learning objectives. Another study by James Fu concluded that the use of ICT in education helps students achieve quality education through effective teaching and learning.⁴¹ As technology allows and encourages students to work more collaboratively, it helped them in developing collaborative skills which helped in their professional lives. Fu further added that technology encourages students to be more open and take risks which is fundamental to any learning in their lives as well. He identified that technology provides a meaningful communication to students, teachers, and administration which helps in the efficient learning of objectives.⁴² There are several advantages of adapting digital learning tools. Students not only become tech-savvy but also become independent learners during the process of ICT incorporation. There are prominent results of correlation between ICT equipped teaching and learning and effective implementation of lesson planning. Both these positively affect students’ achievement.⁴³ It is deduced that the best way to ensure wholesome classroom experience where lesson objectives are fulfilled aptly is when information and communication technology is aligned with lesson objectives. Technological integration with education has a positive impact on education, however there are certain challenges attached to it which pose as obstacles to the implementers. One of the major obstacles is the transition between traditional and ICT enabled curriculum. This transition requires extensive staff training with infrastructural changes and resource availability which may be a challenge to financially deprived institutions.⁴⁴

According to Inas Alkholy, incorporation of multimedia in graphic design curriculum ensures elevated experience of learning to the student and also gives the teacher freedom of exploring

⁴⁰ Geer, R and Trudy-Ann Sweeney. “Students’ Voices about Learning with Technology,” *Journal of Social Sciences* 8, no. 2 (March 26, 2012): 294-303, <https://doi.org/10.3844/jssp.2012.294.303>.

⁴¹ Fu, Jo. Complexity of ICT in Education: A Critical Literature Review and its Implications,” *International Journal of Education and Development Using ICT* 9, no. 1 (2013): 112-125.

⁴³ Cox, Margaret, Mary Webb, Chris Abbott, B. Blakely, Tony Beauchamp, and Valerie Rhodes. “ICT and Pedagogy: A Review of the Research Literature: A report to the DfES (ISBN: 1844781356).” (2004).

⁴⁴ Emre, DiNC. “Prospective Teachers’ Perceptions of Barriers to Technology Integration in Education.” *Contemporary Educational Technology* 10, no. 4 (2019): 381-398.

diverse media. He further highlights that most teachers in the design field face serious limitations related to access to technology in the Middle East.⁴⁵ The subject requires PowerPoint presentations whereas the teachers do not have access to multimedia. The pictorial resources that can be used through incorporating audio-visual prompts is not possible in traditional methods.

During various discussions with professionals of the field in Lahore, at least four main obstacles were identified. Firstly, students who try to make their ends meet find it extremely difficult to manage between studies and freelance designing.⁴⁶ Secondly, when designer graduates encounter market professionals who do not have an academic background but are paid as much as them due to their technical skills, demotivates them.⁴⁷ They find a prominent gap between new software in the market and the ones that they came across in their academic learning. Availability of outdated soft wares in universities, also creates difficulty for students while competing with local and international markets. Thirdly, difficulty lies in the contrast between moral and ethical values they are given in their school versus what they experience in the marketplace.⁴⁸ In universities, students are given conceptual understanding of ethics however in the practical market they need to design products which do not comply with ethical constructs and where services are faked on many levels. Another major issue that creative designing capabilities of designers with degrees are usually out casted by technicians who know the software and are ready to work but for significantly higher rates and wages.⁴⁹

Market stakeholders are of the view that modern curriculum development in the graphic design industry should be aligned with the need for professionalism and accuracy by the end-consumer, requirements of the professional marketplace and that of higher education standards.⁵⁰ Market stakeholders have highlighted the need of building multiple skills in graphic design students including aesthetic faculties, work professionalism, language proficiency, cognitive abilities, and understanding.⁵¹ Graphic

⁴⁵ Alkholly, Inas. "Using Hypermedia in Teaching Art & Design: Baroque Dutch Paintings." *International Journal of Emerging Technologies in Learning (IJET)* 5, no. 3 (2010): 37-41

⁴⁶ Jafri, M. Hassan. Former Head of Design Faculty, National College of Arts. Audio, 2018.

⁴⁷ Hussain, Tazeen. Head of Communication Design Department, Indus Valley School of Design. Audio, 2020.

⁴⁸ Falk, Armin, and Nora Szech. "Institutions and Morals: A reply." *European Journal of Political Economy* 40 (2015): 391-394.

⁴⁹ Leonard, Dorothy, and Jeffrey F. Rayport. "Spark Innovation through Empathic Design." *Harvard Business Review* 75 (1997): 102-115.

⁵⁰ Ferguson, Brooks. *Art, Commerce, and Values: The Relationship between Creativity and Integrity in the Feature Film Development Process*. Pepperdine University, 2004.

⁵¹ Meyer, Michael W, and Don Norman. "Changing Design Education for the 21st century." *She Ji: The Journal of Design, Economics, and Innovation* 6, no. 1 (2020): 13-49.

designers should have these four capabilities: Professional design skills, academic degrees, practical experience, and creative design skills. Without these skills, it would be difficult to survive in the ever-changing arena of design and technology in the modern world.⁵²

Psychological Perspective of Creativity in Graphic Design Education

Creativity is a major component of a human's psychological health. Since creativity is an absolute necessity in graphic design curriculum, it is essential to investigate its psychological and cultural intricacies. Creativity is mostly a by-product of culture. Since an individual's experiences are mostly formed by culture, creativity in turn is formed by cultural impact on an individual. When a person's values and life experiences are connected with his 34surrounding through interaction, it creates creativity. Culture and tradition give birth to folklore which become part of a child's imagination since childhood. This later adds with life experiences and hence forms creativity. In order to nurture problem-solving skills in students, creativity is very important. Most of the university teachers are of the view that creativity and problem solving are fundamentals of graphic designing.⁵³ Since creativity is crucial for diverse solutions and diversity is required to cater the needs of different cultures.

Once a student is enrolled in graphic designing courses, he expects his teacher to teach creativity. However, creativity, according to psychologists, cannot be taught rather nurtured, enabled, and reinforced through effective teaching and learning approaches. To understand the role of creativity in graphic design education, it is essential to first evaluate what drives a designer towards creativity.

Graphic design is often seen as a simple process of manipulating pictures and texts. However, its basic goal is to inculcate aesthetics in a student's language where they learn the order and meaningful solutions for each message created.⁵⁴ The goal of education is to enrich students through creative thinking abilities. It is a complex process to deliver a meaningful message through lines, patterns, colors, texts, shapes, audios, videos, and

52 Cheung, Pun Sin Benson. "The Making of Competent Graphic Designers in Hong Kong: The Transitional Period from Academia to Professional Practice." (2015).

53 Alhajri, Salman Amur. "The Importance of Creativity in Teaching Graphic Design in Arab World." *Design Principles & Practice: An International Journal* 4, no. 1 (2010).

54 Alhajri, Salman Amur. "Investigating Creativity in Graphic Design Education from Psychological Perspectives," *Journal of Arts and Humanities* 06 (January 29, 2017): 69-89, <https://doi.org/10.18533/journal.v6i01.1079>.

54 Kansrirat, Thawatchai and Paiboon Kiattikomol. "Essential Skills of Training Ideas Generation in Graphic Design for Non-Graphic Designers in Thailand" *Global Journal of Engineering Education* 18, no. 2 (2016): 129-35.

much more. Since there are multiple options in graphic design, it is important to equip students with correct methods to explore which medium to use, when, and how. This requires creativity and problem-solving skills to cater specific needs. Idea generation process also requires mental capabilities and problem-solving skills to communicate to different audiences. Understanding interconnectedness of ideas and their practicality in the real world is also a significant skill which needs to be part of graphic design education. This competence is broadly covered under the head of creativity in the discipline of psychology.⁵⁵

In four years, undergraduate program Pakistani students are taught packaging, advertising, publication, and visual communications. All of these require effective skills of international standards. Since all signs, displays, and posters require an effective message with correct selection of colors, text, and technique, a graphic designer is expected to have an aesthetical as well as market-oriented eye.

According to Jesenka Pibernik, graphic designers “are delegated with the responsibility for the context and content of design messages.”⁵⁶ Since a designer is responsible for the perceptions of the message in the minds of the audience, it is essential to have excellent cognitive skills. Graphic designers are expected to be creative and at the same time competitive in their approaches towards design. Since creativity is seen as a function of culture, the definitions for creativity change with cultural shifts. Different cultures perceive creativity with varied approaches, therefore creative minds are those who are seen as problem solvers in the context of their surroundings. Thus, the role of creativity remains fundamental in graphic design education.

Studies suggest that “there exists a continuous need to explore the cross cultural and indigenous elements of creativity.”⁵⁷ This aids in observing the effect culture have on creativity and its link with students’ psychology as well. Such findings are very meaningful for curriculum developers who work to build a skill set for design students. Graphic design education aims to develop creativity in students through appropriate curriculum design and effective teaching methodologies. These definitions are Western models of creativity which promote problem solving and inventiveness as major features of creativity. Graphic design education primarily helps to solve problems at hand and while this is seen as a fundamental aspect of creativity, this is not the only factor contributing to it. James Barnard emphasized that “creativity

⁵⁶ Pibernik, Jesenka, Diana Milcic, and Josip Bota. “Pressure Toward Creativity: Individual/Group Work in Student Design Competition,” in *DS 66-2: Proceedings of the 1st International Conference on Design Creativity (ICDC 2010)*, 2010.

⁵⁷ Alhajri, Salman Amur. “Investigating Creativity in Graphic Design Education from Psychological Perspectives.” *Journal of Arts and Humanities* 6, no. 01 (2017): 69-85.

could be appropriately thought of as a mere cultural production and advancements in the field of graphic design are examples of cultural production.”⁵⁸

Curriculum developers mainly focus on the core skills required for the specific subject. For graphic designing, it is problem-solving and creativity which leads to best communication of the message. Curriculum development in graphic designing must be targeted towards excellent cognitive skills to ensure manifestation of creativity in the projects. Subject-specific teaching and learning methodologies should be introduced in curriculum to cater particular learning objectives and effective classroom interactions. The curriculum for graphic designing should include group activities in order to foster collaborative skills with effective communication. When learners perform problem solving activities in groups, it simulates studio experiences where a team works towards solving a particular objective. It is recommended that open-ended problem-solving challenges along with group tasks are assigned to graphic design students, so they learn to communicate while collaborating with their peers. This will also encourage peer-learning. When learners’ cognitive skills are well groomed, they become enabled to easily adapt to any changes required to deal with professional life situations. In North America, workshops have become part of graphic design education.⁵⁹ These workshops not only help students actualize their special potentials while increasing their contemporary knowledge set pertinent to graphic design education. These workshops help students build their cognitive skills to the level that they become able to understand the core skills related to graphic design and how these skills are relevant in the marketplace.

From this chapter one can see that graphic design education in Pakistan started as a craft to contribute industrial requirements, assumed an academic identity and then became market-oriented research and practice. It is intriguing that the changing relationship of graphic design education and its corresponding industry has not been documented.

The absorption of graphic designers in the communication industry of Pakistan and the hundreds of students graduating in the discipline create this illusion that the process is much tangible and result oriented. Even a cursory observation reveals that this surge is due to the economic forces and not due to the creative and aesthetically inspiring potential of the discipline. There is a need to examine graphic design education and its impact on industry in the local setting to move on to third stage, where we could intelligently intervene in the domain of graphic design education and thereby improve the face of the communication industry.

⁵⁸ Barnard, Malcolm. *Graphic Design as Communication*. Routledge, 2013.

⁵⁹ Park*, Chris. "The Graduate Teaching Assistant (GTA): Lessons from North American experience." *Teaching in Higher Education* 9, no. 3 (2004): 349-361.

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